

X-shaped Radical Offshore wind Turbine for Overall cost of energy Reduction

D9.1

Project website and social media

 <https://xrotor-project.eu>

 @XROTORProject

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Table of Contents

About X-ROTOR.....	5
1 Introduction	8
2 Project website	8
3 Social Media.....	10
4 Conclusion.....	11
5 Bibliography	11

About X-ROTOR

X-ROTOR: “X-shaped Radical Offshore wind Turbine for Overall cost of energy Reduction” is a Horizon 2020 funded project which aims to develop a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept.

The X-ROTOR project is led by University of Strathclyde (UK) in partnership with Norwegian University of Science and Technology (Norway), Delft University of Technology (Netherlands), University College Cork (Ireland), Fundacion Cener National Renewable Energy Centre (Spain) and GE Renovables España (Spain).

As the effects of climate change are becoming ever more visible, Europe has raised its target for the amount of energy it consumes from renewable sources from the previous goal of 27% to 32% by 2030. Offshore wind energy can play a key role in achieving the EU target and contribute to the required 40% reduction in CO₂ emissions. However, to achieve the previously mentioned targets the cost of offshore wind must be reduced. The X-ROTOR concept provides a direct route to drastically reducing both capital and operating costs of energy from offshore wind.

The project runs for three years from January 2021, during which time, the concept will be developed through a holistic consideration of technical, cost, environmental and socio-economic impact aspects.

If proven feasible, X-ROTOR will, as a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept, create new opportunities for the European wind energy industry and play an important role maintaining the EU’s position as global technological leader in renewable energy, reducing greenhouse gas emissions and decarbonising the EU economy.

For more information see <https://xrotor-project.eu>

Description of the deliverable and its purpose

This deliverable D9.1 “Project website and social media” has been prepared within the context of work package 9 of the X-ROTOR project which is concerned with communication of the project objectives and activities, and dissemination of the results which arise therefrom.

In particular this deliverable presents the project website (<https://xrotor-project.eu>) which will be launched on 31 March 2021. The initial basic website will be further developed and enhanced over the life of the project. The deliverable additionally provides an overview of the project’s approach to the promotion of its activities and results on social media.

List of acronyms

CMS	Content Management System
DoA	Description of Action
URL	Uniform Resource Locator, colloquially termed a web address
UX	User Experience

1 Introduction

This brief report is intended to introduce the project website (Deliverable 9.1) for the Horizon 2020 funded X-ROTOR research project. As such, the second section provides such an introduction, explains the incremental development approach adopted, outlines the structure of the website and provides a link to the site which will go live in a soft launch at the end of March 2021. The third section comprises a short outline of the project's approach to social media and this is followed by a brief concluding section.

2 Project website

Task 9.2 as outlined in the project's Description of Action (DoA) involves the set-up and maintenance of a project website to *'serve as the main interface among the project and the stakeholders who are interested in the work and achievements of X-ROTOR, and also act as a communication and dissemination channel for the project's results as well as involving and enlarging the stakeholder community.'*

A website is increasingly considered an essential (if indeed, not *the* essential) component in research communication, engagement and dissemination. It offers an easily accessible location where interested parties may find out more about the project and follow its progress during its realisation (Khoo, 2014). This encapsulates the primary objective of any research project website, which in essence is all about raising the visibility of the project¹. A secondary objective for research project websites – albeit one which is unstated and rarely explicitly considered – is enhancing the digital identity, or so-called e-visibility, of the individual contributors (see e.g., Luzón, 2018 who discusses constructing online academic identities), of the participating research groups (see e.g., Lorés-Sanz and Herrando-Rodrigo, 2020)², and indeed of the research funding programmes and agencies. In the specific case of Horizon 2020 project, this would relate to the requirement for promotion of the action, and visibility of EU funding as required by Article 38 of the model grant agreement.

In keeping with the aforementioned objectives for research project, Task 9.2 as detailed in the DoA, says *'the project website will be designed and continuously updated in such a way to include'* information about the project, interface with X-ROTOR social network presence, project blog, public results, news items, links to relevant sites, calendar of events, *etc.* The website for the X-ROTOR project therefore can be said to have the following objectives:

- Raise awareness about the project and its objectives;
- Communicate about the project's research and outreach activities;
- Promote engagement with industry and societal stakeholders;
- Disseminate the results of the project;
- Acknowledge funding and support of the Horizon 2020 programme;

¹ In addition, Cummings and Kiesler (2007) observe that shared technologies such as a project website can improve the collaborative activities of researchers.

² Lorés-Sanz and Herrando-Rodrigo (2020) offer an interesting exploration of the how such e-visibility considerations are reflected in the website content of a selection of research projects funded under the Horizon 2020 programme.

- Publicise the involvement of the participating partners (and where appropriate, individual contributors).

The project website will be designed and maintained using the WordPress Content Management System (CMS). The WordPress platform is a feature-rich, multifaceted, accessible CMS that allows the development of both small and simple websites and larger, more complex sites.

A Responsive Web Design approach has been taken, meaning that the coding is such that the website will be presented differently depending on the viewing device. This is so that content will be resized or hidden in accordance with the formatting and presentation layers protocols on device of different sizes *i.e.*, desktops, tablets, and smartphones.

The X-ROTOR project website will go live on 31 March 2021 on the following URL: <https://xrotor-project.eu>. In keeping with the continuous development of the site envisaged in the DoA, at this early stage of the project, this will serve as a soft launch³ of the website, with an initial basic layout and design which will be enhanced and improved over the coming months as the project progresses. A soft launch strategy is considered an valuable approach for website development (McMahon, 2021) – it is used as a means of ‘testing’ a web site, ascertaining the features and design elements preferred by partners and external stakeholders and facilitating a gradual tweaking of the UX and potentially the redesign of components of the site.

The first iteration of the website will comprise all the usual sections expected of a research web page *e.g.*, landing page, overview of the project, profile of partners, details of news and events, link to project outputs, contact details, *etc.* Other sections such as blog posts, *etc.* will be added as the project matures. However, as would be expected given the early stage of the project, many of these sections (*e.g.*, project outputs) will have minimal content, if any.

The website has the structure as outlined below, with each section having a link to one another.

- HOME (Landing page, brief introduction, social media feed, funding acknowledgement, links to policies)
- ABOUT (Information about the project, its objectives and activities, funding acknowledgement)
- PARTNERS (A brief description of each project partner with logo and link to their website)
- OUTPUTS (Project public deliverables, and other outputs of interest arising from the project)
- NEWS & EVENTS (All news and events both from the project, and those of interest to the project)
- CONTACT (A registration form to contact the X-ROTOR project)

The site will be linked to the website analytics tool in order to track the number of visitors, identify their languages and locations, and determine devices used for browsing the website.

³ A soft launch is a practice whereby a website (or other product) is released incrementally with minimal publicity and initially to a limited audience. This allows for an opportunity to (re-)consider all aspects of the product and to finetune it before re-launching with publicity.

3 Social Media

While there is no one definitive definition⁴ of what constitutes social media, McCay-Peet and Quan-Haase (2016, p. 17) offer a comprehensive overview saying that ‘*social media are web-based services that allow individuals, communities and organizations to collaborate, connect, interact, and build community by enabling them to create, co-create, modifies (sic), share and engage with user-generated content that is easily accessible.*’ Such an all-encompassing perspective means that as Mollet *et al.* (2017, p. 15) put it, ‘*the answer to the question of what isn’t covered by the term social media is actually very little.*’ Indeed, they go on to observe that many traditional communication tools are increasingly adding social dimensions to their offering. Social media can be categorised into a number of different types⁵ (albeit evolving functionalities meaning that these categories increasingly overlap). The most interesting to a research project are perhaps those which facilitate microblogging and sharing of media. Provision for social media use for the project is outlined in Task 9.3 of the DoA, which says ‘*Social media positioning will help the project to disseminate and communicate its objectives, developments and results in a faster way than regular channels.*’ The task description envisaged the use of three social media platforms for the project, namely: Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube. The strategy for the use of each of these social media platforms is outlined below.

Twitter (<https://twitter.com>) will be used as a principal communication tool for the project, providing links to news arising from the project and occasional links to related projects and news items of interest. A Twitter account – [@XRotorProject](#) – has been set up for the project. It is planned that this account will be used sparingly in the initial part of the project, slowly building a presence and a following. It is envisaged that the principal use will be over the second half of the project once results start to emerge.

LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com>) is a professional networking site, its focus on business and employment content differentiates it from other platforms and represents a useful communication route for a project focused on technological development such as X-ROTOR. Due to the nature of LinkedIn, it is not intended to establish a project-specific profile / group on this platform. As the project progresses, news items on the research being undertaken will be prepared periodically and shared through the existing personal LinkedIn accounts of the participating researchers. This will be coordinated by UCC as the WP9 lead.

YouTube (<https://www.youtube.com/>) represents a good way of reaching an audience through the sharing of short videos and animations. At this stage of the X-ROTOR project, it is too early to establish a YouTube channel. However, it is recognised that this platform

⁴ Although there is general consensus that it involves ‘*online communities – groups of people interacting online to communicate and share information and ideas*’ (Mollett *et al.*, 2017, p. 12).

⁵ Social media can be categorised into a number of different types including e.g., social networking sites (e.g., Facebook, LinkedIn), microblogging (e.g., Twitter), media sharing (e.g., YouTube), blogs (e.g., WordPress), social news (e.g., Reddit), *etc.* (Mollett *et al.*, 2017, p. 18)

will prove a useful means of outreach as the project matures. In the second half of this year as research progresses, and stakeholder engagement is initiated, a project-specific YouTube channel will be established to complement the project other online presence in the website and social media.

4 Conclusion

A website for the X-ROTOR research project has been designed, developed and soft-launched with initial content on 31 March 2021. The website has been designed to provide easy access to key project information news and events. Following this soft launch, the design will be tweaked and amended to take account of feedback from both internal and external stakeholders and revised to incorporate increasing content which will be available as the project progresses. The website will be regularly updated throughout the project with the latest news, events, and outputs. It will act as a key communication channel to the public, stakeholders and wider communities for all project information. The project's principal social media presence will be on the Twitter platform, this will be complemented by partners' posts on the LinkedIn platform. As the research develops a project YouTube channel will be used to promote the X-ROTOR concept and publicise research outputs. In the course of this online outreach both website and social media analytics will be employed to track and analyse engagement with the project.

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